

SIMULATION OF COMPOSITE DAMAGE DUE TO LIGHTNING STRIKE

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ABSTRACT

The use of composite laminates for primary aircraft structures like fuselage implies to take into account the lightning strike hazard. Lightning strike is a threat to both metallic or composite structures, and requires careful considerations from a certification standpoint. The main difference between metallic and composite materials lies in the poor conductivity properties of the latter. However only few public research activities focus on the study of lightning direct effects on the integrity of carbon fibre reinforced polymers (CFRP) structures. Recent studies at Onera led to the development of a magneto-hydrodynamic model in order to simulate the lightning channel. The output of this model (direct heating, electric current and impose pressure to the lightning arc) can be used as boundary conditions for a finite element (FE) simulations of lightning strike on composite material. The aim of this study is to propose first a comprehension model of the thermo-electric phenomena focusing on the resulting damaging pyrolysis due to the thermo-electric boundaries conditions imposed by the lightning channel. Pyrolysis is a major damaging mechanism affecting thermal and electric conductivities as well as mechanical properties. Pyrolysis is driven by (i) dielectric breakdown due to high electric fields and conductivity anisotropy and (ii) volume severe heating due to the Joule effect. To take into account the evolutions of the boundaries conditions (Joule heating) and the material state, the thermo electric analysis is performed by a partitioned coupling algorithm which links an electrostatic finite element analysis with a transient thermal finite element analysis. First comparison of these simulation results with experimental data will be presented.

1. INTRODUCTION

The use of composite laminates for primary aircraft structures like fuselage implies to take into account the lightning strike hazard. Lightning strike is a threat to both metallic and composite structures, and requires careful considerations from a certification standpoint. The main difference between metallic and composite materials lies in the poor conductivity properties of the latter. However only few public research activities has been devoted to the study of lightning direct effects on the integrity of carbon fibre reinforced polymers (CFRP) structures [1–7].

Hiranno *et al.* [1] demonstrate by an experimental approach the similarity between the impact damage and the lightning strike damage. The authors also investigate the influence of the impulse waveform and conclude that the fiber damaged area and damage thickness is dominated by the peak current of the lightning strike, while the resin deterioration area and the delamination projection area are dominated by the electrical charge and the action integral of waveform, respectively. Feraboli *et al.* [3] also analyze the influence of the peak current of the lightning strike on the damage area of CFRPs for plane coupon or bolted joined coupons.

Ogasawara *et al.* [4] used a fully coupled electrical and thermal finite element analysis software in order to estimate the matrix damage area due to the impulse waveform. In their analyzes, they only applied as boundary conditions the experimental waveform of the impulse current. For the thermal behavior of the composite, they identify the pyrolysis behavior using a thermogravimetric analyzer and classical empirical equations for estimating the pyrolysis kinetics of the resin. In order to take into account the dielectric breakdown, the authors assume that the electrical conductivity of the material

depend linearly from the temperature of resin degradation (600°C) to the temperature of sublimation of the fiber. This is the reason why a fully coupled electrical and thermal analysis is needed.

Abdelal and Murphy [5] also used a fully coupled electrical and thermal finite element analysis. They analyze the effect of the copper mesh protection system on the degradation of the composite. As Ogasawara *et al.* [4], the authors take into account the evolution of the pyrolysis behavior of the composite laminate but also take into account the thermal behavior of the protection system (melting, evaporation, and ablation). Nevertheless they don't take into account the influence of the electrical breakdown in their simulation. Nevertheless, they adopted a more rigorous modeling approach than Ogasawara *et al.* [4].

The aim of the present work is to demonstrate the influence of the electric breakdown on the estimation of the thermal behavior of composite laminate subjected to lightning strike. The first section deals with the physics involved in the lightning strike on composite structure, the second part describes the numerical model adopted and the electrical breakdown models proposed. The third section focuses on the first results obtained with this first numerical approach.

2. THE MULTIPHYSICS PROBLEM

The work of Chemartin *al* [7-8] permits to strengthen how the loading due to a lightning strike is complex. As shown on Fig. 1, the structure is submitted to:

- strong electric currents resulting in resistive heating due to Joule effect ;
- severe direct heating due to the plasma channel ;
- hydrodynamic pressure also due to the plasma.

Figure 1: Scheme of the physics involved during a lightning strike within the material

This figure illustrated the different physics needed to be taken into account in order to simulate the damage due to lightning strike on composite laminated structures. Structural dynamics is not treated in this early work. On the opposite to metallic material due to the poor electrical conductivity of the matrix, the Joule effect has a major role in the evolution of the temperature inside the material. This is the reason why the estimation of the current density field is essential. Moreover, the anisotropic electric behavior of the composite ply (the electrical conductivity of the fiber is 10^3 times higher than the resin one) implies a high gradient of electric potential in the thickness of the composite laminate which leads to electrical breakdown. This electrical breakdown induces an instantaneous pyrolysis of

the matrix but improves not only the electrical conductivity but also thermal one of the material due to the char formed.

As mentioned previously, the influence of the heating due to the plasma channel (more than 30000 K in the plasma channel) and the Joule effect need to be taken into account in a transient thermal problem in order to estimate the pyrolysis of the material and the damage inside the composite material. In this preliminary work, we only focus on the effect of the electrical breakdown on the thermal behavior of the material. Nevertheless and as mentioned previously the physical material parameters (electric, thermal or mechanical) depend on the temperature of the material and imply to have a coupling between these different physics. Hence a partitioned coupling algorithm is set up to account for (i) the influence of Joule effect and breakdown on the heat transfer problem and (ii) temperature and pyrolysis on the electrostatic model. Direct heating and electric current due to the plasma channel are taken as boundary conditions from the magneto-hydrodynamic model developed in [7-8].

3. THE NUMERICAL MODEL AND MATERIAL BEHAVIOURS

3.1. The electrostatic model

An electrostatic conduction model is used to determine the current distribution within the laminate by following the Ohm's law:

$$\vec{j} = \underline{\sigma}_e \vec{E} \quad (1)$$

where σ_e is the electrical conductivity of the material, \vec{j} the current density and \vec{E} the electric field (the gradient of the electrical potential). Due to the material anisotropic behavior, the electrical conductivity order 2 tensor of the material could be expressed with the following form:

$$\underline{\sigma}_e = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_f^o & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma_m^o & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \sigma_m^o \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

Matrix in which the subscript f corresponds to the fiber direction and the m subscript corresponds to the fiber transverse direction (matrix direction). The exponent o defines the pristine behavior of the material. The electrical fiber behavior is 3 orders of magnitude higher than the matrix one and the current tends thus to flow in the fiber direction within the top ply where it is injected. This generates electric fields that have a high component in the out-of-plane direction and leading to electric breakdown. A simple maximum criterion is then retained to predict the electric breakdown in the material:

$$\|\vec{E}\| > E_m^{bd} \quad (3)$$

Where E_m^{bd} is a material parameter. Since this phenomenon is sudden, it is treated in an explicit way; when criterion is met at the end of a time increment, breakdown is only taken into account in the next one by changing conductivity. Then, only the two material states can be distinguish for this damage phenomenon (virgin or not) and a Boolean damage variable d_{bd} is defined. The evolution of the electrical conductivity is then defined with the following expression:

$$\underline{\sigma}_e^{\text{eff}} = \underline{\sigma}_e^o + d_{bd}(\underline{\sigma}_e^{py} - \underline{\sigma}_e^o) \quad (4)$$

Where the exponent py points out the pyrolysis state of the material. Table 1 and Fig. 2 report the electrical material parameter identification for this study, values which are mainly extracted from [6].

Material Parameters	Values
σ_f^o	See Fig. 2
σ_m^o	See Fig. 2
σ_m^{py}	$1.6 \cdot 10^{10} \text{ S.m}^{-1}$
σ_f^{py}	$1.6 \cdot 10^{10} \text{ S.m}^{-1}$
E_m^{bd}	$19.7 \cdot 10^6 \text{ V.m}^{-1}$

Table 1: : Electrical material parameters for a carbon/epoxy material at the ply scale [6]

Figure 2: Evolution the electrical conductivity as function of the temperature [6]

3.2. The thermal model

The thermal behaviour of the composite material is based on a transverse isotropic thermal conduction law (in the fibre direction). Like the electrostatic model, two material parameters λ_f^o and λ_m^o are sufficient to define the thermal behavior in absence of damage. When the material is pyrolyzed by electric breakdown, its thermal behavior is then considered as isotropic with k^{py} as thermal conductivity. In order to transpose this damage behavior, the effective thermal conductivity is expressed as:

$$\lambda^{\text{eff}} = \lambda^o + d_{bd}(\lambda^{py} - \lambda^o) \quad (5)$$

In order to take into account the thermal degradation, a classical thermokinetic law is proposed and is based on Arrhenius formulations in which the coefficient have been identified by TGA. For the carbon/epoxy material of interest (T700/M21), three chemical reactions have been observed and modeling by the following equation system:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{d\alpha_i}{dt} = A_i e^{E_i/T} [1 - \alpha_i(t)]^{n_i} \\ \alpha_i = 1 - \frac{w_i}{w_i^0} \\ d_{py} = \sum_i w_i \alpha_i \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Equations in which A_i and E_i are material parameters, α_i are reaction growth variable and w_i are mass percentage by solid phases. In this model, three solid phases are considered. The two first ones describe the fiber and matrix phases and the last one describes the char phase. The d_{py} variable represents the material loss of mass. In order to propose a complete model, Equation 5 is modified and replaced by this new set of equations:

$$\begin{cases} \underline{\lambda}^{\text{eff}} = \tilde{\underline{\lambda}} + d_{bd}(\underline{\lambda}^{py} - \tilde{\underline{\lambda}}) \\ \text{with: } \tilde{\underline{\lambda}} = (1 - d_{py}) \underline{\lambda}^o + d_{py} \underline{\lambda}^{py} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

The identification of the thermal degradation is deduced from the more general model of Biasi [9]. Table 2 and Fig. 3 report the identification of the material parameters for the thermal behavior.

Material Parameters	Values
λ_f^o	Voir Fig. 3
λ_m^o	Voir Fig. 3
λ^{py}	Voir Fig. 3
C_p	Voir Fig. 3
A_i	[9.032 10 ⁵ ; 5.672 10 ⁵ ; 2.004 10 ⁵] s ⁻¹
E_i	[1.055 10 ⁵ ; 2.033 10 ⁵ ; 1.677 10 ⁵] J.mol ⁻¹
n_i	[1.8 ; 1.8 ; 1.]

Table 2: Thermal material parameters for the T700/M21 carbon/epoxy material at the ply scale

Figure 3: Evolution the specific heat and the thermal conductivity as function of the temperature for a carbon/epoxy material at the ply scale [6]

Like for the thermal behaviour, the electrical behaviour depends on the evolution the thermal degradation by pyrolysis of the matrix. Equation 4 is then modified in order to depend on the evolution of the d_{py} variable. The effective electrical conductivity is defined by:

$$\begin{cases} \underline{\sigma}_e^{\text{eff}} = \tilde{\underline{\sigma}}_e + d_{bd}(\underline{\sigma}_e^{py} - \tilde{\underline{\sigma}}_e) \\ \text{with: } \tilde{\underline{\sigma}}_e = (1 - d_{py}) \underline{\sigma}_e^o + d_{py} \underline{\sigma}_e^{py} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

The thermal problem is solved by the heat equation for which a supplementary term is added and described the Joule heating by internal heat generation:

$$\begin{cases} C_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} - \underline{\lambda} : \underline{\Delta} T = P \\ \text{with } P = -\vec{j} \cdot \vec{E} \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

Relations in which C_p is the specific heat and P is the Joule internal heat. This relation outlines one more time the importance to have coupling algorithm to solve the thermo-electric problem.

3.3. Thermo-electric partitioned coupling

Electrostatic and transient thermal models are solved with different instances of the finite element solver Z-set [10]. Both models need to be coupled since breakdown and temperature have an influence on electrical and thermal conductivities as mentioned previously. The partitioned coupling algorithm aims at linking the two instances of Z-set and is illustrated in Fig. 4:

- a first electrostatic increment is performed. d_{bd} and Joule heating volume specific power (P) fields are transferred to the heat transfer model;
- the temperature and the d_{py} fields are transferred to the electrostatics computation.

Electrostatic increments are still solved in an explicit way thus resulting in successive resolutions of linear problems. However thermal analysis is highly non-linear and may require subcycling with adaptive time steps Δt_h .

Figure 4: Weak coupling scheme of electrostatics and transient thermal models

In order to avoid numerical errors due to the evolution of the electrical breakdown field computed by an explicit algorithm, the time step needs to be very small. Nevertheless due to the electric and thermal loading imposed by the lightning arc, such time steps are mandatory.

4. APPLICATION

In order to demonstrate the validity of this approach, a quasi-isotropic laminate of 8 plies has been considered. The composite plate is a square of 400 mm side length. A constant temperature of 300 K and a null electrical potential is imposed on the circumferential plate sides. On the upper side of the composite plate, the lightning arc channel imposes the following normal current density (j_n) and normal heat flux (q_n) on a circular surface of variable radius R_c :

$$\begin{cases} j_n(t) = \frac{218810 (e^{-11354t} - e^{-647265t})}{\pi R_c^2(t)} & \text{in } A.m^{-2} \\ q_n(t) = 10j_n & \text{in } J.m^{-2} \\ R_c(t) = 9\sqrt{t} & \text{in } m \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

This relations are approximations of the output of the magneto-hydrodynamic model proposed by Chemartin [7-8]. The evolution of the injected current and of the infection radius is illustrated on Fig. 5 and satisfies the theoretical waveform of simulated lightning arc strike impose by certification authorities.

Figure 5: Time evolution of the injected current and the injection radius.

Figs. 6 illustrate the degradation of the matrix by electric breakdown or by the apparition of char at 10 μs. The α_2 is the reaction growth variable dedicated to the apparition of char in the material. On the Fig. 7 b, the two fields have been superposed in order to have the matrix damage pattern at the end of the simulation ($t = 10$ s). We can observe that in a first step, it is the electric breakdown damage that appears and in a second step, it is the thermal degradation that evolves. It is worth mentioning that in absence of damage in the matrix, the predicted temperature field is unrealistic. By this approach, the maximum of temperature inside the material is realistic. The electric breakdown field inside the material avoids high temperature on the upper side of the composite panel by increasing the transverse electrical conductivity and permit to reduce the electric field in the first plies.

Figs. 7 compare damage pattern observed on composite plate due to simulated lightning strike impact to our numerical results. Even if fibre damage or delamination are not take into account in these preliminary analyses, the matrix damage simulated is in qualitative good agreement with the matrix damage experimentally observed by [4].

Figure 6: Fields of pyrolysis due to electric breakdown or due to thermal degradation (α_2) at $t = 10$ μs

a/ Pattern of damage due to simulate lightning strike on carbon/epoxy laminate observed experimentally [4]

b/ Pattern of damage at $t = 10$ s. Pyrolysis due to electric breakdown is in red color and due to thermal degradation is in black color.

Figure 7: Comparison between numerical and experimental damage pattern.

9 CONCLUSIONS

In this work, a specific care has been focused on the estimation of a realistic thermal behavior of a composite structure subjected to lightning strike impact. This is a reason why, an efficient numerical strategy has been developed and permits to take into account all the different physics involved in this multiphysics problem, *i.e.* the electrical and thermal problem. The numerical strategy is based on a partitioned coupling problem that considered in a first-hand an electrostatic problem and in an other hand a transient thermal problem.

The electrostatic problem permits to compute the current density in the material and takes into account the apparition of instantaneous pyrolysis of the matrix due to electrical breakdown. A very simple criterion is used in order to modelling this matrix damage that implies a very sudden improvement of the electrical and thermal conductivities. Independent from the breakdown phenomenon, the electrical conductivity is dependent of the temperature.

In the transient thermal problem, Joule effect field and the state of the material estimated by the electrostatic problem are taken into account in order to estimate the temperature inside the material. Thermally activated pyrolysis is taken into account by a classical autocatalytic set of chemical reactions. The evolution of the thermal degradation leads to an increase of the transverse thermal and electrical conductivities. Thanks to the electrical breakdown phenomenon, the electric current density and the heat flux can flow in the thickness of the composite. It limits the temperature gradient in the composite and implies hot spot in the opposite face of the lightning strike. Moreover, the comparison with experimentally matrix damage pattern shows a reasonably good agreement with the matrix damage pattern simulated with the proposed approach.

This work is a first step in order to simulate the damage effect of the lightning strike on composite laminate and strengthens the influence of the breakdown in the analysis. Further works will take into account the mechanical loading due to the lightning and permit to estimate the damage due to this complex loading, the damage tolerance of the structure and to propose numerical design tool for composite laminate.

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